

ERIC FARRELL

The Institution of Engineers of Ireland
CORK REGION

The Geotechnical Society of Ireland

One-Day Seminar

Glenbeigh Records
Management

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Investigation of Karst Areas and Remedial Action Adopted for Roads and Structures

February 27th. 1995

Lecture Theatre G10
Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering
University College Cork

The Institution of Engineers of Ireland
CORK REGION

The Geotechnical Society of Ireland

SEMINAR

Investigation of Karst Areas and Remedial Action Adopted for Roads and Structures

PROGRAMME

- 10.30 REGISTRATION/COFFEE
10.50 OPENING ADDRESS
Mr JD Kennelly, Chairman, Cork Region IEI

SESSION I

Chairman : *Mr Ross Galbraith*
Chairman, Geotechnical Society of Ireland

- 11.00 The nature of Karstic environments and the associated environmental problems
Dr David Drew, Trinity College Dublin
- 11.45 Site investigation for projects in Karst areas
Mr Bernard Murphy, Bernard Murphy & Assoc.
- 12.30 Discussion
- 12.45 Lunch

SESSION II

Chairman : *Mr Michael Long*
Ove Arup & Partners, Dublin

- 2.00 A Database for Subsidence Sinkholes in the Cork District
Dr Tony Beese, Carraigex Ltd
- 2.30 Foundation solutions in Karstic Limestone
Mr Jack O'Leary, Malachy Walsh & Partners
- 3.00 Remedial measures applied to the engineering solution of Karst problems.
Dr Michael Creed, UCC
- 3.45 - 4.30 General Discussion

Tony Beese

Rock core
1) No quantitative measurements of water subsurface to reach to core the unit
2) hydrogeology
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Remedial measures applied to the engineering solution of Karst problems

Dr Michael Creed, Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, UCC

**THE NATURE OF KARSTIC ENVIRONMENTS
AND THE ASSOCIATED ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS**

*Dr. David Drew
Trinity College Dublin*

Q 1) How do you hydrogeologically model karst aquifer

THE NATURE OF KARSTIC ENVIRONMENTS AND THE ASSOCIATED

ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS DAVID DREW T.C.D.

2) Register of Karst features

Karst areas are a unique case of water modifying the nature of the rock fabric as well as vice-versa.

Given an initial structure the hydrological and geochemical systems operate on the rock to produce a karst hydrological and landform system that is wholly distinctive.

THE BASICS OF KARSTIFICATION

1. Limestones are soluble in acidified rainwater, pure limestones dissolve more readily.
2. As the limestone is dissolved by water it is removed as invisible solute load.
3. Water percolating through to bedrock will selectively enlarge preexisting fissures in the rock.
4. Eventually a network of fissures is opened up allowing water to circulate freely underground.
5. All excess rainfall travels by underground routes to its reappearance at springs.
6. With time the underground drainage system becomes more integrated and efficient, comparable to a surface drainage system.

Indicators of karstification include :

1. Lack of surface runoff in streams.
2. Fragmentation, disorganisation and localisation of surface drainage features.
3. Solutional origin for landforms on all scales.
4. Importance of subterranean hydrology and geomorphology in determining surface features.

The degrees of dominance of the above determine whether an area is non - karstic partly karstified or holokarst

Typically:

1. The sense and control of the landscape is underground in caves and conduits.
2. Maximum karstification is in the epikarst and the top of the saturated zone.
3. Past karstification may be preserved (change in watertable or infilling) and may later be reactivated to a greater or lesser extent.

Karst in Ireland

40% of the island, 75% of it on the lowlands, the rest is plateau karst.

Fluvio, Nivo, Glacio, Fossil but no Holokarst.

The accompanying map shows (speculatively) the minimum extent of karstified limestones.

1. Not known when karstification started but certainly in Tertiary (more than 2 million years ago)- with a lower base level and subtropical climate = deep karstification.

2. Then glacial disruption of conduits + recharge mechanisms maybe formerly doline (enclosed depression) oriented + discharge areas.

3. Thus a pre-Quaternary degree of karstification + degree of post-glacial recovery + post-glacial karstification especially in uplands

Plateau karsts - best defined but least important economically

eg Sligo-Leitrim - table land dissected by glaciated valleys.

eg Cuicagh massif, rim of limestone around younger rocks.

eg Burren

Lowlands: karst topography largely unknown due to infilling

1. Economically the most significant area in terms of its impact

2. Knowledge is patchy and unco-ordinated except for parts of west and southeast.

3. Suspected to be very widespread.

4. Nowadays a mixture of active modern karst and ancient karst being reactivated hydrologically.

5. Evidence: - gravity anomalies, mining fissures, quarry fills, caverns ancient caves.

KARST CAUSES PROBLEMS

1. *Water resources are unpredictable in terms of location, quantity and quality.*

2. *Because the dynamic of the landscape is underground and invisible the usual 'certitudes' become unpredictable:*

eg Strength and behaviour of overburden and bedrock

eg Drainage conditions

eg The effects of imposed change: - construction - drainage

" Expect the Unexpected

"Cavernous limestone karst ... is the terrain type whose geomorphological understanding becomes an art, matured only through experience, and then applied sensitively and individually at each new site assessment".

THE MOST COMMON PROBLEMS IN KARST AREAS

- Affecting buildings, roads, reservoirs etc.
- May result from interaction with a presently active karst system
or from the reactivation of a non-functional (fossil) system

1. *Slope failure - unpredictable - due to solutional detachment of limestone strata.*

2 *Gradual or catastrophic sinkhole development & subsidence*

Differential subsidence of a construction

- *due to rockhead topography or*
 - *due to suffosion by drainage water or*
 - *due to cavern collapse (overloading) or*
 - *due to dewatering of overburden/rock*
-

AREAS OF IRELAND IN WHICH KARSTIC PROCESSES ARE OR WERE DOMINANT

(Areas 1, 2 and 3 were at least partly karstic in pre-Quaternary times)

- 1. Present day highly karstic
 - 2. Present day partly karstic
 - 3. Present day non-karstic or not known
- Lake

**SITE INVESTIGATION FOR PROJECTS
IN KARST AREAS**

*Bernard Murphy, M.Sc, D.I.C., M.I.E.I, F.G.S.
Bernard Murphy & Associates*

**Site Investigation
for
Projects
in
Karst Areas.**

Paper presented
by Bernard Murphy M.Sc, D.I.C., M.I.E.I, F.G.S.

at the
Seminar on

***Investigation of Karst Areas and Remedial
Action Adopted for Roads and Structures***

(Institution of Engineers of Ireland &
Geotechnical Society of Ireland)

held in
Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering
University College Cork.

on Monday 27th February 1995.

1) answer spais &
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from B/H

2) Categories

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change of reserve

- i.e. volume of
mass of rock

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considered

3) from hole

**Bernard Murphy & Associates
Unit 6B, Woodbine Park
Blackrock
Co. Dublin.**

**Tel. (01) 2600020
Fax. (01) 2839943**

Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to outline a methodology for designing effective site investigation programs for construction projects in areas underlain by karstified limestones. Guidelines for assessing the degree of karstification based on surface features are proposed. This assessment is examined in relation to the nature of the proposed project and the risks involved, and the degree of site investigation required is thereby decided.

The specific geotechnical, geophysical and hydrogeological site investigation techniques that are available are rated according to their cost and effectiveness. Each technique is then discussed, and some examples presented. Finally, a flowchart for the site investigation process is presented, which allows for constant review and updating of the program and of the risks involved.

Definitions

Karstification is comprehensively defined by Assad & Jordan (1994) as, "*an aggregate of geological processes either naturally or artificially in the earth's crust and on its surface due to chemical, physicochemical (processes), and/or under diverse geological and climatic conditions through time and is expressed through the formation of openings, the destruction and alteration of the structure of the rocks, and through the creation of a particular type of groundwater circulation and a characteristic regime of drainage network and characteristic regional topography*".

It occurs extensively in Ireland, mainly in areas of Carboniferous Limestone, particularly purer micritic-type limestones, and is characterised by the presence of sinkholes, turloughs, underground rivers, and a range of other topographical and drainage features.

Degree of Karstification

Primary factors affecting the degree to which karstification develops are listed by Drew and Daly, 1993, as :

- (a) the type and solubility of the limestone
- (b) the degree of jointing, faulting and bedding
- (c) the chemical and physical character of the groundwater
- (d) the rate of water circulation
- (e) the subsoil cover

Therefore areas of pure, highly jointed limestone overlain by thin or no soil cover and subject to heavy rainfall are likely to develop high degrees of karstification. Such areas can subsequently be covered by glacial deposits to give a buried karst topography.

The degree of karstification can be assessed indirectly based on the presence of the various geotechnical, geomorphological and hydrogeological features listed and rated in Tables 1 & 2 (Working Group on Karst, 1995). Once an initial estimate of the degree of karstification is made, usually from a desk study and walkover survey, the problems arising from the interaction between it and the proposed development are considered.

Nature of the problem

Karstification can give rise to two types of problems (Benson & Yuhr, 1993), which affect either:

- (a) structural integrity (such as sudden or gradual collapse of the rock or overburden)
- (b) groundwater flow (such as the entry of pollutants or the escape of contained water)

An example of the upward migration of a cavity due to fluctuating waterlevels and gravity fall, taken from Culshaw & Waltham, 1987, is shown in Fig 1.

FIG. 1. Progressive development, from left to right, of the two types of subsidence sinkholes, creating either a slow subsidence or an instantaneous dropout.

Category of the Proposed Development

Proposed developments are divided into three categories based on Eurocode No. 7 for Geotechnical Design, 1994:

Category 1 covers small and relatively simple structures with a maximum design column load of 250kN, such as houses, agricultural buildings and drainage works.

Category 2 includes conventional types of structures and foundations such as bridges, roads, earthworks and some tunnels.

Category 3 consists of large or unusual structures such as power stations, dams, etc.

(It is acknowledged that the Eurocode 7 classifications themselves are based on the presence or absence of abnormal ground conditions, but the categories are used as a convenient way of rating proposed developments.)

Factors related to the nature of the proposed development, that should be considered, in conjunction with the developers and the design team, include:

- (a) the potential of the proposed development to reactivate dormant karst systems. This typically happens due to disruption of existing drainage patterns and in particular, through the introduction of a downward component of flow.
- (b) the nature of the activity at the proposed development and the scope for minimising the risks attached to these activities in relation to the degree of karstification present.
- (c) the costs involved at all stages of the proposed development.

Degree of risk

Risk is defined in Jefferies (1994) as the "combined effect of the chance of an accident and the damage caused by that accident". This definition has been used in conjunction with the category of the proposed development and the estimated degree of karstification, to construct a Risk Matrix (Table 3).

Objectives of the Site Investigation Process

The general objectives of the process should include the following:

- (a) to minimise the risks involved, either by avoiding or reducing exposure to karstified zones.
- (b) to minimise the risks involved by providing adequate information for the design and construction process.
- (c) to focus site investigation activity on critical areas.

Specifically the Site Investigation should include the following:

- (a) outline the extent of the karstified zone on a regional and local basis
- (b) identify controlling factors, such as geology, controlling joint sets, etc.
- (c) estimate the degree of karstification, the vertical thickness of the karstified zone and the extent to which the karstification processes are currently active.
- (d) identify the nature and thickness of the overburden and its degree of consolidation.
- (e) map existing surface and subsurface drainage patterns, monitor groundwater levels and flow, and record seasonal variations.
- (f) locate existing clay, water or air filled cavities in the rock.
- (g) locate existing clay, water or air filled cavities within the overburden and if possible determine their rate of migration.
- (h) provide detailed information over the zone of influence of the foundations of load bearing structures.

Discussion of Site Investigation Techniques

Table 3 indicates the degree of site investigation required for each degree of risk category. The various site investigation techniques are listed in Table 4 in order of cost and effectiveness for each degree of Site Investigation. Each technique is discussed in Tables 5A-C, with reference to their relative advantages and disadvantages. Examples are given of their application, with particular emphasis on the geophysical techniques.

The target to site ratios for karst investigation are usually very small, with a typical cavity being of the order of 2-10m diameter. For example, a 10m diameter cavity on a 1ha site has a detection probability of 1/100, requiring up to 100 borings to achieve a confidence level of 90% (Benson & Yuhr, 1993).

To achieve a significant confidence level, without the excessive expenditure described above, requires the use of a combination of direct and indirect site investigation techniques. Primary among these are the Desk Study and Walk Over phase of the investigation. These allow for rapid acquisition of large amounts of relevant data, on a regional or local basis. Geophysical and other remote techniques can also be used to outline the extent and degree of karstification on regional to local basis, and provide specific targets for the more costly drilling techniques.

The relevant combination of techniques, used in the proper order, allow the site investigation to be conducted with maximum efficiency. Correctly guided focussing of resources is a key element in improving the overall cost-effectiveness of a site investigation program especially when investigating karst terrains.

Conclusion

The need to review the information as it is being produced is paramount, together with a constant re-evaluation of the degree of risk, based on the additional information being provided. A flow-chart outlining these relationships is presented (Fig 2), which provides for constant review and updating of the program and of the risks and costs involved.

Site Investigation in karstified areas requires a systematic approach to determining the regional, local and specific setting of the proposed development. This should involve a phased approach to the investigation which uses a combination of indirect and direct techniques. The techniques selected should reflect the degree of risk associated with the project and the aim should be to obtain the optimum and most relevant information at each stage of the investigation.

References

- Assaad, F.A & Jordan, H. 1994 Karst terranes and environmental aspects; Environmental Geology 23: 228-237.
- Benson, R.C & Yuhr, L. 1993 Spatial sampling considerations and their applications to characterizing fractured rock and karst systems; Environmental Geology 22: 296-307.
- Culshaw, M.G. & Waltham, A.C. 1987 Natural and artificial cavities as ground engineering hazards. Q.J.E.G., 20, 139-150.
- Drew, D & Daly, D 1993 Groundwater and Karstification in Mid-Galway, South Mayo and North Clare. G.S.I. Publications
- Env 1997-1: Eurocode 7 1994 Geotechnical Design - General Rules; European Committee for Standardization, CEN/TC 250/SC 7, N 126.
- Jefferies, M. et. al. 1994 Risk Assessment: Where are we, and where are we going; Golders Associates U. K.
- Working Group on Karst 1995 Report in Prep. T.C.D./G.S.I.

**Table 1 - Estimation of Degree of
Karstification based on Karstic Features**

No.	Description of Feature.	Degree of Karst.
1	<i>Karren on Exposed Rock.</i>	<i>Low</i>
2	<i>Minor Clay Filled Discontinuities (<200mm).</i>	<i>Low</i>
3	<i>Small Springs.</i>	<i>Low</i>
4	<i>Minor Water/Air/Clay Filled Cavities (>200mm).</i>	<i>Medium</i>
5	<i>Enclosed Depressions.</i>	<i>Medium</i>
6	<i>Turloughs.</i>	<i>Medium</i>
7	<i>Losing Streams.</i>	<i>Medium</i>
8	<i>Major Water/Air/Clay Filled Cavities.</i>	<i>High</i>
9	<i>Collapse Features.</i>	<i>High</i>
10	<i>Dry Valleys.</i>	<i>High</i>
11	<i>Swallow Holes.</i>	<i>High</i>
12	<i>Caves.</i>	<i>High</i>

Table 2 - Degree of Karstification
based on Hydrogeological, Geotechnical
Geomorphological Features.

	Degree of Karstification		
	Low	Medium	High
Hydrogeology	<i>Small Springs</i>	<i>Losing Streams</i>	<i>Dry Valleys</i> <i>Swallow Holes</i>
Geotechnical	<i>Discontinuities</i>	<i>Cavities</i> <i>Depressions</i>	<i>Major Cavities</i> <i>Collapse Features</i>
Geomorphology	<i>Karren</i>	<i>Turloughs</i>	<i>Caves</i>

Category of Project - Degree of Damage Likely.

Table 3 - Risk Matrix.

Degree of Karstification	Category1	Category2	Category3
	Minor Engineering Projects. (Houses, Offices, etc.).	Intermediate Engineering Projects. (Roads, Reservoirs, etc.).	Major Engineering Projects. (Oil Refineries, Dams, Power Stations, etc.).
Low	Low	Medium	High
Medium	Medium	Medium	High
High	High	High	High

**Table 4 - Site Investigation Rating
- Technique Evaluation.**

Techniques			
Direct	Low	Medium	High
Desk Study	X	X	X
Walkover Survey	X	X	X
Trial Pits	X	X	X
Probes	X	X	X
Rotary Percussive		X	X
Cable Percussive		X	X
Rotary Coring		X	X
Speleology			X
Indirect			
EM31 Conductivity	X	X	X
VLF-EM Profiling	X	X	X
EM34 Conductivity	X	X	X
VLF Resisitivity	X	X	X
Resistivity Soundings	X	X	X
Resistivity Profiling		X	X
Seismic Refraction		X	X
Ground Probing Radar		X	X
Microgravity			X
Downhole Logging			X
Seismic Reflection			X
Groundwater			
Desk Study	X	X	X
Walkover Survey	X	X	X
Dye Tracing	X	X	X
Falling/Rising Head Test		X	X
Packer Testing		X	X
Downhole Logging		X	X
Water Balance Modelling		X	X
Inter-Borehole Dye Tracing			X
Pump Tesing			X
Numerical Modelling			X

Table 5A - Description of Direct Methods in relation to Karst Site Investigation.

Method	Strata	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	
Desk Study	Overburden & Bedrock	Collation of all available sources of information e.g. Air Photos, GSI Maps & memoirs Prev. Investigation, Research, OS Maps & Placenames	Quick, Cheap and Very Effective way of establishing background information on site before direct invest starts	Lack of detailed information Requires ground truthing	Low
Walk Over	Overburden & Bedrock	Survey of area of interest re: geomorphological features drainage patterns quaternary & bedrock outcrops Obtain Photos of Imp Features	Quick, Cheap and Very Effective way of establishing preliminary on-site info. and investigating features identified in Desk Study	Can be Difficult to obtain access at early stage in project.	
Trial Pits	Overburden & Weathered Rock	Excavation using tracked or wheeled machine	Quick, Cheap and Very Effective way of establishing preliminary on-site info. and obtaining upper layer information including samples	Limited Depth of Penetration Can cause considerable disturbance Point Information	
Probes	Overburden & Weathered Rock	Percussive Technique involving penetration of rods into ground with/without sampling/blow counts.	Quick, Cheap and Very Effective way of establishing preliminary on-site info. and obtaining upper layer information	Limited Depth of Penetration Lack of Direct Control Point Information	
Rotary Percussive (Wagon Drill)	Rock	Rock Drilling Technique involving penetration of button bit gen. w/ air flush and no recovery (blow back of rock chips) (rate of penetration)	Rapid Investigation of Rock particularly cavity location Relatively Inexpensive	Lack of Recovery Point Information	Medium
Cable Percussive (Shell & Auger)	Overburden & Weathered Rock	Overburden Drilling Technique used for depth to bedrock meas. sampling of overburden Strength Measurements (SPT)	Relatively rapid technique Relatively inexpensive	Limited depth of penetration stopping on boulders Point Information	
Rotary Coring	Rock	Drilling Technique used to recover rock cores at a range of diameters using diamond impreg. bits and liners to aid recovery Generally water flush.	Generally Reliable method to recover samples of rock allowing visual ident. & testing of samples & in-situ Can provide prn. info - flush ret	Relatively Expensive Point Information Difficulty in recovery poor quality material	
Speleology	Rock	Exploration of Cave Systems by Divers	Allows mapping of the distribution of underground caves and caverns	Only suitable for large scale features	High

Table 5B - Description of Geophysical methods in relation to Karst Site Investigation.

Method	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	
EM31 Conductivity	Measures near surface (<6m b.g.l.) ground conductivity	Quick, cheap, does not require ground contact. Good for shallow rock	Limited penetration, low resolution relative to cavity size	LOW
VLF-EM Profiling.	Maps location of linear conductive features, such as faults.	Quick, cheap, does not require ground contact. Good for regional features.	Low resolution, affected by other geological variations and topography.	
EM-34 Conductivity	Measures ground conductivity	Quick, rel. cheap, does not require ground contact. Has better penetration than EM31 (up to 50m).	Low resolution relative to cavity size. Affected by topography .	
VLF Resistivity	Measures ground resistivity	Quick and cheap, good penetration indicates bedrock type and depth some reports of direct detection.	Interpretation difficult in areas of complex overburden/geology, best for reconnaissance.	
Resistivity Soundings	Gives variation and thickness of material with depth using ground current measurement.	Gives good material type and thickness information. Can indicate watertable/fissuring.	Slower and more expensive than EM methods. Needs good elec. contrasts.	
Resistivity Profiling	Gives variation and thickness of material with distance using ground current measurement.	Can give detailed image of lateral and vertical variations in subsurface if used in hi-res pseudosection mode.	Slower and more expensive than EM methods. Needs good elec. contrasts.	Medium
Seismic Refraction	Indicates nature, type and thickness of material from measuring seismic velocities	Can give reasonably accurate bedrock profile as well as information on the stiffness/quality of soil/rock	Penetration may be limited, also requires good contrasts and increase in velocity with depth	
Ground Probing Radar	Produces cross-sections based on closely spaced reflections of EM pulses.	High lateral and vertical resolution Fast survey rate. Direct detection possible.	Penetration limited by wet or conductive ground. Can be expensive.	
Microgravity	Measures variations in gravity field caused by density variations in the subsurface	Responds directly to cavities and mass deficits. Direct detection possible.	Slow and expensive. Subject to bedrock and surface topography effects.	High
Downhole Logging	Logs of density, rock quality, bore-diameter, joint fill, etc.	Accurately locates and measures extent of voids around borehole, presence of clay fill, etc.	May require PVC casing of holes, of limited use in some situations.	
Seismic reflection	Produces cross-sections based on reflections from overburden and rock layers.	Good resolution and continuous coverage, good depth penetration.	Requires good velocity/density contrasts Slow and expensive.	

Table 5C - Hydrogeological methods in relation to Karst Site Investigation.

Method	Description	Advantages	Disadvantages	
Desk Study	Note any large temporal or spatial variations in waterlevels, stream base-flow, well yields, spring flows.	Quick, cheap, gives regional overview	Not site specific	Low
Walkover	Note type of drainage and density, also waterlevel fluctuations in streams, turloughs, etc	Quick, cheap, site specific	Access problems, no specific groundwater head information obtained.	
Dye Tracing	Inject dyes (e.g. leucophor) into karst feature and check emerging drainage for traces.	Cheap. Gives information on drainage patterns, catchment and storage.	Slow, results can sometimes be inconclusive.	
Falling/Rising Head Test	Measure fall/rise in water levels over time	Quick, cheap, indicates hydraulic parameters	Gives approximate results only, small area tested, affected by regional fluctuations.	Medium
Packer testing	Measures flow rates in sealed zone at different input pressures.	Quick, can give flow rates of fissure zones. Indicates main inflow zones.	Gives approximate results only, small area tested, affected by regional fluctuations.	
Downhole logging	Camera, flow meter, conductivity meter lowered down hole.	Indicates main inflow zones. Can measure effective thickness of aquifer.	No specific parameters tested, borehole dependent.	
Water Balance Modelling	Calculates/compares discharge, recharge and throughflow rates.	Quick, cheap, helps to develop conceptual model.	No specific parameters tested.	
Inter-Borehole Dye Tracing.	Measure traveltime and concentration of injected dye between boreholes.	Indicates flow velocity and storage capacity of aquifer.	Expensive, results can be inconclusive Needs large number of boreholes. effects.	High
Pump Testing	Pump out aquifer and measure drawdown in observation boreholes	Gives yield information and location of productive fissures and extent of aquifer	Conventional analysis not fully accurate in karst, expensive, can induce collapse.	
Numerical Modelling	Construct computer model from available data.	Outlines groundwater flow patterns and allows modelling of dilution, dispersion of pollutants.	Models can be very complex, especially in karst.	

Fig 2 - Flowchart of Site Investigation Procedures in Karst Regions.

**A DATABASE FOR SUBSIDENCE SINKHOLES
IN THE CORK DISTRICT**

*Dr. Anthony P. Beese
Carraigex Limited*

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- any correlation
with chemical
composition
of ^{horizon}

A database for subsidence sinkholes in the Cork district

Anthony P. Beese

Carraigex Ltd., 5 Fitzgerald Place, Old Blackrock Road, Cork

SYNOPSIS: Costly damage has resulted from subsidence sinkholes forming in the vicinity of structures in the Cork district. Consequently, there is an increasing amount of information available from site investigations. In this paper, it is proposed that an informal database, structured according to previous experience in the Cork district, may be useful in future investigations; helping to identify (1) the physical characteristics of subsidence sinkholes as distinct from other ground subsidences, (2) critical areas, (3) possible causal factors, (4) cost-efficient site investigation methods, and (5) appropriate treatment methods.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the local Irish dialect *slogaire* is the name for a sinkhole. According to the Irish Dictionary by Ó Dónaill (1977), the word is masculine and means “a swallower, gulper; glutton”. The plural *slogairí* may be the source word for the anglicization *sluggie*, a local name for sudden ground failures. The Irish word suitably describes the character of a *subsidence sinkhole*, a term defined by Waltham (1989) as *failure of a soil or weak rock into underlying cavernous limestone*. An equivalent term is *subsidence doline* in the sense of Jennings (1971).

Subsidence sinkholes form in buried karst terrain. Typically, voids in the underlying limestone bedrock are activated by changes in hydrogeology. In the Cork district, the voids migrate upwards through glacial soils, by processes such as progressive ‘arch’ and ‘roof-collapse’, downwashing and ravelling. When they reach ground level subsidences are formed.

2. THE SINKHOLE HAZARD

Approximately one or two hundred sites with subsidence sinkholes may have activated in the Cork district since 1970. This estimate is based on limited information and may be conservative. Several hundreds of sites with sinkhole development have probably occurred in the wider Munster area over the same period, but the available information away from the Cork district is even more sketchy than that within it.

There are anecdotal reports of subsidence sinkholes as far back as the 1920s, but whether the frequency of the sinkhole event is increasing or not is yet to be substantiated. However, the incidence of *induced* sinkholes on construction sites and in other disturbed environments suggests that the sinkhole event has become more common¹ There are fewer reports of ‘*natural*’ sinkholes opening up in agricultural landscapes, but this is partly due to the lesser financial consequence of this type. It could be argued that these so-called ‘*natural*’ sinkholes are classified as such only because no man-made triggers have been identified for them. For

¹ Induced sinkholes are sinkholes accelerated or caused by man (Newton, 1987).

example, there is preliminary evidence to suggest that sinkholes can be activated merely by ploughing a field formerly used for pasture (see below).

Costly damage results from karst subsidence. Sinkholes can be adjacent to or underneath roads, railways, structures and services. As yet no fatalities or injuries have been reported. However, there have been a few accidents. In the 1920s, near Rathcormac, about 25 km northeast of Cork City, a man and horses ploughing a field are said to have dropped down into a large sinkhole. In a second case, Gerard McCarthy of Cloyne reports that in the 1970s, when he walked over ground that had been ploughed for the first time in many years, he fell as the ground beneath him gave way; the Cloyne Caves are underneath his land. The implications for vehicles travelling on roads and railways are obvious.

3. THE PROPOSED DATABASE

The diagnosis of subsidence sinkholes, a partly hidden phenomena, and the distinction between them and other types of ground subsidence, can be problematic. Consequently, there has been some confusion over selecting a suitable and cost-efficient method of assessment. A wide-ranging database is proposed in this paper as part of a systematic approach. Since sinkhole behaviour and treatment are dependent on many interacting factors including regional geology, the current database is organised according to accumulating data from case histories within the Cork district. Suggested subjects for the database are presented in Table 1.

The aims of the database are firstly, to provide an enquiry structure at the initial desk study stage of the site investigation, and secondly, to assist in the design of any ground investigations and remedial works. Dougherty and Perlow (1987) recommended collection of available sinkhole data as a first step in dealing with future sinkhole problems, and Ketelle and Newton (1987) compiled a database for sinkhole characteristics in East Tennessee.

Results for data collected from twenty-five sites with sinkhole development in the Cork district are discussed below. These case histories are drawn from: (1) fourteen sites surveyed by the author, all of these associated with new structures or disturbed ground conditions, (2) personal communications by Civil Engineers for six more 'construction' sites, and (3) anecdotal histories and site visits for five large areas of farmland with 'natural' sinkholes, which may or may not have been man-induced.

Table 1. Suggested database subjects.

Group Heading	Subjects
Distribution	reference, general and detailed locations, development type
Sinkhole Topography	site topography, sinkhole morphology, number and trends
Overburden	factual description, type, thickness
Bedrock	factual description, type, epikarst type
Hydrogeology (Other Factors)	date of occurrence, weather, water table, vegetation/topsoil, services, structures etc.
Site Investigation	desk studies, site visit, trial pits, boreholes, geophysics
Remedial Works	treatment of sinkholes, services and structures; grout records

Figure 1. Distribution of subsidence sinkholes in the Cork and Cloyne Synclines. The unshaded portion of the figure defines ridges of sandstone and siltstone.

4. GENERAL DISTRIBUTION

All the examples of sites with sinkhole development in the Cork district coincide with narrow valleys underlain by Lower Carboniferous Limestone. Structurally, these valley tracts can be treated as synclines. The features of the sinkholes in the Cork and Cloyne Synclines are best known (Figure 1), but scattered examples have been investigated further north in the 'Rathcormac' and 'Fermoy' Synclines. As already stated, part of the reason for the known concentration of sinkholes in the Cork Syncline is the high density of recent developments there, including housing, industrial estates and roads.

5. SINKHOLE TOPOGRAPHY

The sinkholes identified here are at elevations of between approximately 8m and 57m above sea level. Prior to development, most sinkhole environments consist of gentle, drift-covered slopes adjacent to irregular limestone knolls. At some locations, ground failures are adjacent to fields showing localised depressions and changes in vegetation. These are thought to be environments where the overburden is not thick enough to blanket the underlying karst features.

Physical features useful in the recognition of sinkholes are catalogued by Newton (1987). The morphology of the subsidences in the Cork district is typically a circular to elliptical opening near ground level, and a steep to subvertical 'tube' below ground level. In trial excavations steep failure surfaces through the overburden are sometimes visible. The majority of sinkholes are relatively small, at between 0.3m and 3m in diameter at ground level, but there are several cases of a subsidences measured at approximately 5m to 10m across. Where drops in ground level have been measured, values of between 0.2m and 2m are typical. Using steel bars, the loose soil in sinkholes has been probed easily down to depths of 5m.

In all except three cases, between one and five sinkholes are recorded at each site. The subsidences often occur in groups, and some sinkholes reactivate over a period of several years. Three sites have between six and thirteen sinkholes, but two of these are road realignments covering large areas. Significantly, all three sites with large numbers of sinkholes are at a similar stratigraphic level in the Cork Syncline. Interpreted trends for two or more sinkholes are most often ENE to E, and NW to N, orientations which subparallel some of the underlying bedrock discontinuities (see below).

6. OVERBURDEN

Using the terminology of BS 5930 (1981), the engineering soils at sinkhole locations may be summarized as slightly silty to very silty, sandy, subrounded to subangular sandstone GRAVEL (or gravelly SAND) with cobbles, usually compact, sometimes stratified. These soils are granular to slightly cohesive and are interpreted as glacial or glaciofluvial deposits. Trial excavations have demonstrated how compact made ground, overlying glacial deposits can slow down the progress of overburden voids up to ground level. Glacial soils north of Cork City appear to be siltier than those further south. This feature may explain anecdotal evidence of differences in sinkhole behaviour near Rathcormac and Fermoy; the degree of cohesiveness of soil layers affect the mechanism and scale of their failure (Newton, 1987; Waltham, 1989).

The thickness of overburden overlying bedrock is variable, ranging from less than 1m to 15m. In most cases it is possible to show that the overburden is relatively permeable and unsaturated down to rockhead levels, at least in the critical zones where sinkholes have formed.

7. BEDROCK

All the sites appear to be underlain by limestones of Lower Carboniferous age (Dinantian Stage). Mudbank limestones of the Waulsortian Complex are typical. Using the terminology of BS 5930 (1981) these rock types may be summarized as streaky grey, jointed and massive, generally fine grained LIMESTONE (calclutite), strong to very strong, locally cleaved, locally bedded, occasionally dolomitized. As well as being generally fine-grained, the limestones are almost pure and, therefore, are prone to cavitation (see Waltham, 1989). However, certain narrow stratigraphic intervals appear more susceptible to sinkhole formation than others. For example, in the Cork Syncline, there are nine sites with soil failures overlying the same sequence of bedded limestones with thin cherts, stretching over an east to west length of some 20 km. Again, at least five sites with sinkhole development are near the edges of the Fermoy, Cork and Cloyne Synclines, that is within the lowest fine-grained limestone beds of the Waulsortian Limestone sequence.

An area of farmland near Rathcormac has three sites with subsidence sinkholes which are aligned along a northwest trend, demonstrating that ground collapses can be concentrated along fault trends as well as stratigraphic trends. Clearly, preferential weathering of certain bedrock features is significant.

The limestones have a long history of post-Carboniferous weathering (Higgs and Beese, 1986) and associated epikarst features, developed along steep to subvertical dipping discontinuities (faults, bedding and joints), include openings into air- and water-filled cave systems often several metres across, networks of soil-filled fissures up to several metres across, and large soil-filled dolines, several tens of metres across. It is significant that cave systems

(Coleman, 1965) and/or faulted palaeokarst with abundant infilled fissures and dolines, are nearly always identifiable in the general vicinity of sites with sinkholes.

8. HYDROGEOLOGY

Hydrogeological changes in surface and ground water play a key part in the formation of subsidence sinkholes (Newton, 1987; Waltham, 1989). Newton subdivides induced sinkholes into two types: firstly, those resulting from water-level decline, and secondly, those resulting from diversion or impoundment of surface drainage.

Both types or a combination of both types are recognizable in the Cork district. So far, no systematic research has been completed on the factors influencing sinkhole formation and the hydrogeology of areas with 'natural' sinkholes is not well known. However, the following general comments are offered.

For unconfined aquifers, sites with the major water table within typically thick overburden are less prone to sinkhole development. However, temporary lowering of the water table down to bedrock level is a significant contributory factor. It is possible that in some areas there may be progressive dewatering owing to major drainage schemes, and to an increasing demand for groundwater for industrial and agricultural purposes.

Cyclical periods of dry weather followed by heavy rainfall seem to have triggered subsidences in some cases. French Drains and leaking services are also well established triggers, presumably causing downwashing of loose soil. Similarly, stripping of vegetation or topsoil increases the amount of infiltration of surface water, and obstructions such as foundations, embankments and pavement edges can redirect runoff and focus water flows.

9. SITE INVESTIGATION

Experience to date suggests that a systematic investigation to form an overview of the site is most appropriate. The aim is (1) to eliminate other possible causes of subsidence such as made ground, anomalous soil conditions, and other epikarst phenomena such as rare sinkholes owing to collapse of bedrock, (2) to confirm the scale and extent of the karst problem, and (3) to identify the essential hydrogeology of the site.

Desk studies and reconnaissance surveys of the site should be completed in advance of any ground investigation, with the evolving database being used as a guide. The whole of the site should be investigated, as broken services in between buildings have caused foundation failures, requiring expensive remedial works.

A full ground investigation as an initial approach is not recommended. In many cases, ground investigation may be limited to carefully located trial pits and/or a limited number of rotary cored boreholes. While 'probe' drilling may be an important aspect of remedial works, it is no substitute for rotary cored boreholes, interpreted by a geologist familiar with the local geology, a view shared by Fischer et al (1987). Also, careful monitoring of 'grout-take' during remedial works such as pressure grouting may obviate the need for ground investigation.

Geophysical surveys have not been successful in resolving the typically small cavities of the Cork district and are better employed to 'map' the general geological context such as depth to bedrock and depth to the water table. In other words, results have not been sufficiently definitive.

10. CONCLUSIONS

Data compiled from a limited number of sites with a history of subsidence sinkholes has shown up some significant trends. In particular, the engineering geological context of karst subsidence is becoming clearer. It is hoped that this promise will encourage engineers to contribute many other case histories both from the Cork district and from the wider Munster area. Written, photographic and anecdotal information is of use. A more complete record of sites with subsidence sinkholes would provide a valuable resource for future desk studies.

11. REFERENCES

- Beese, A.P., Creed, M.J. In press. A database for subsidence sinkholes near Cork, Ireland. Proceedings of the XI ECSMFE Conference, Copenhagen, 1995.
- BS 5930 (1981). *Code of Practice for Site Investigations*. British Standards Institution, London.
- Coleman, J.C. (1965). *The Caves of Ireland*. Anvil Books Ltd., Tralee.
- Dougherty, P.H., Perlow, M. Jr. (1987). The Macungie Sinkhole, Lehigh Valley, Pennsylvania: cause and repair. In Beck, B.F., Wilson, W.L. (eds) *Karst Hydrogeology: Engineering and Environmental Applications* A.A. Balkema, Rotterdam, 425–435.
- Fischer, J.A., Greene, R.W., Ottoson, R.S., Graham, T.C. (1987). Planning and design considerations in karst terrain. In Beck, B.F., Wilson, W.L. (eds), *ibid.* 323–329.
- Higgs, K., Beese, A.P. (1986). A Jurassic microflora from the Colbond Clay of Cloyne, Co. Cork. *Irish Journal of Earth Sciences* 7, 99–109.
- Jennings, J.N. (1971). *Karst: An Introduction to Systematic Geomorphology*. The MIT Press, London.
- Ketelle, R.H., Newton, J.G. (1987). Inventory of karst subsidence in the Valley and Ridge Province of East Tennessee. In Beck, B.F., Wilson, W.L. (eds), *ibid.* 25–29.
- Newton, J.G., (1987). Development of sinkholes resulting from man's activities in the Eastern United States. *U.S. Geological Survey Circular* 968, Denver.
- Ó Dónaill, N. (1977). *Foclóir Gaelige-Béarla*. An Roinn Oideachais, Dublin.
- Waltham, A.C. (1989). Sinkholes on limestone. In *Ground Subsidence*. Blackie, Glasgow, 17–40.

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FOUNDATION SOLUTIONS IN KARSTIC LIMESTONE

*Mr Jack O'Leary
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FOUNDATION SOLUTIONS IN KARSTIC LIMESTONE

GEOLOGY OF TRALEE

It is well known that the immediate Tralee area is difficult from the point of view of building construction. Tralee town is located on an outcrop of Carboniferous Limestone. In this rock, solution cavities and swallow holes are a common feature. These limestone deposits in Tralee are the result of erosion which has permitted survival of limestone at lower levels and the outcropping of old red sandstone of the Slieve Mish mountains at higher level. Inland, the Namuriam Shale outcrop as the ground rises. To the west of Tralee town, the limestone passes below sea level to form the floor of Tralee Bay.

To a large extent, the soils of Tralee basin are of glacial origin. However, estuarine deposits on the flat lands around the bay also occur. As a consequence of these latter features, it is frequently found, in the low lying areas around the town, that there are intermediate zones of mixed glacial and water laid estuarine soils occurring. This mixture can lead to extremely difficult foundation conditions. Further inland, on the outskirts of the town, the glacial soils predominate. These are no less difficult in themselves given the presence of cavernous limestone at depth.

FOUNDATIONS - PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

In any foundation assessment in Tralee, a variety of foundation options must always be investigated. The least difficult situation occurs where rock is at the surface or at shallow depth. Once the integrity of this rock is proven, then conventional strip or pad foundations are possible. A far greater problem arises when the rock is in excess of 5 to 6m below surface level and where the overburden must be examined with a view to providing a foundation option. At that stage, strip, pad, raft or even piled foundations must be considered.

In this presentation, a number of case studies are examined. These range from domestic or speculative housing to more substantial public buildings. The site investigation data, pertinent to these buildings, is presented. The foundation options are discussed and the ultimate solutions used are outlined.

Prior to moving on to the case studies, it is opportune to examine the limited use of piled foundations in the Tralee area. For domestic or speculative housing, the author is not aware of any development in Tralee where piling has been used. On other more substantial buildings in the Town, piling has been examined and discarded as an option. Notwithstanding this, there are a number of important buildings in the town where piling has been successfully used. In these, the Designers have obviously accepted that very substantial variations in the piling lengths will occur due to the occurrence of anomalous limestone at depth. Equally, given that driven piles are usually used in these situations, the Designers must be satisfied that a pile set is being achieved on substantial bedrock and not on boulders or heavily broken rock. This author has always considered that there is an inherent contradiction in carrying a concentrated pile load down to anomalous limestone. The preference has always been to spread the load at a higher level and minimise the stress at the lower level.

DOMESTIC AND SPECULATIVE HOUSING

The site highlighted in this presentation (Ref. Figures 1 - 5) is particularly difficult given that approximately 1.2m of fill overlies soft silty clays and silts. Bedrock, such as it is, occurs at approximately 9 - 10m below existing ground level. Likewise, it will be noted that the original topsoil was not stripped when the site was filled approximately 10 years ago. Other housing sites in the Tralee area would be not quite as difficult as this. A typical situation would consist of 5 - 6m of silty clays overlying the limestone rock. The quality of the silty clays could vary substantially over the extent of the foundation excavation with possibly numerous soft pockets occurring. Foundation solutions are discussed hereunder.

- (1) The easiest scenario is where the rock occurs at the surface or at depths of less than 1.5m below ground level. Here, the quality of the rock can be checked by boring and conventional strip or pad foundations can be provided. This scenario is limited enough in the Tralee area given the possibility of huge variation in the rock profile and sudden changes in depth over very short lengths on the foundation excavations.
- (2) A trench fill type solution as illustrated in Figure 6 has been extensively used by the author in poor ground conditions. Trench fill involves excavating the foundations to ground of reasonable bearing capacity and replacing the excavated material with well compacted limestone hardcore, placed in 225mm layers. Generally, the width of the excavation would be in excess of the strip width, thus

ensuring good load distribution. Standard strip foundations can then be cast at a higher level, thereby minimising expenditure in otherwise difficult foundation conditions.

Some designers prefer to use leanmix concrete as the trench fill material, presumably on the basis that minimal control is needed on the quality of the leanmix. This view is not shared by the author.

In the first instance, the difference in cost between using hardcore and leanmix could be as high as £2,000 per house, obviously depending on the depth of the excavation. For a Developer with a 100 house plan or for a private person with a limited budget, such an additional cost can be prohibitive. Equally, the technical benefits of using leanmix are very doubtful. The hardcore is more flexible and ensures better load distribution at soft locations. Equally, the hardcore will penetrate into the sides of the trench and into the base of the trench giving a more monolithic foundation with no sudden interface as occurs between overburden and leanmix.

There are, however, some downsides in using trench fill hardcore. In the first instance, the author would always use limestone, 100mm down, as the fill material. This material is of a standard quality with the chances of getting defective material being limited. It is necessary to ensure that it is properly compacted. In a trench excavation, say 2m deep, this is difficult. The lower levels can only be compacted using the back bucket of the hymax. This is not an entirely desirable situation. It is important that a roller, vibrating to 10 tonnes, should be used at the lowest safest level to ensure compaction of the limestone fill.

The trench fill solution would equally not be feasible in very poor ground, say, of a peaty nature. Here, the peat would not provide adequate passive resistance on the sides of the trench. In this scenario, total excavation of the very soft material and replacement over the extent of the house and the footpath with compacted limestone has been used by the author. Such a solution is illustrated on figure 7. Notwithstanding the additional hardcore involved, this has often proved to be a viable and economic solution because, in very poor ground situations, the use of a suspended ground floor slab would otherwise have to be examined.

- (3) In figure 8, a form of compensated raft has been illustrated. The author has used this solution in situations where only minimum excavation of soft overburden has taken place. A monolithic raft, 300mm thick, reinforced with mesh top and bottom, is used. The hardcore layer over the raft and the additional power floated floor slab provides space to bring out the waste pipes and other services. Equally, these additional layers provide a downward pressure of approximately 10kN/m^2 to counteract the haunching effect of the raft itself. The net result is that the raft will exist in a form of unstable equilibrium with little and no tendency to displace vertically.
- (4) The house, in figure 9, is presented as a typical foundation inspection. This house is being constructed in an area of well known swallow hole activity. It highlights the need to have a competent contractor on site to carry out the work. Also, the foundation should always be inspected over its full extent and should be probed at numerous locations using an iron bar. The spacing of these probes should be of the order of 3m, reducing if the ground conditions are found to be good.

SUBSTANTIAL PUBLIC BUILDINGS

The second part of this lecture concentrates on foundation options for more substantial public buildings in the Tralee area. Three are illustrated.

- (1) Siamsa Tire, the new National Folk Theatre, a £1.4m development.
- (2) The proposed Kerry County Council Office Extension to the Ashe Memorial Hall, Tralee. This was substantially aborted and a new development was carried out at Rathass.
- (3) The new Kerry County Council Offices at Rathass, a £3m development.

All three of the above buildings were characterised by difficult foundation conditions involving soft and cavernous overburden material overlying cavernous limestone. Ultimately, on all three, a raft type foundation was proposed. This followed a comprehensive investigation of other options. In Siamsa, a driven pile option was examined and was discarded on cost grounds (£80,000 extra). In discarding the pile option, it was recognised that it would have been difficult to cost control anyway given the anomalous limestone at depth. In the Kerry Co. Council offices at the Ashe Memorial Hall, test piling was carried out to monitor vibration on the adjacent building. This piling failed to reach a set notwithstanding the fact that site investigation data indicated rock almost certainly occurring at average 6m depths.

The presentation highlights the site investigation data pertaining to these three developments and explains the preferred foundation solution. In arriving at these solutions, an additional case study is also presented; a tank farm development at Fenit. Here, compacted hardcore was used to make up a substantial change in rock profile. (figure 16). The net pressure on the limestone hardcore was of the order of 125kN/m^2 over a 16m diameter area. This effectively corresponded to a plate test of that loading over the whole area. The differential settlement across the tank was virtually non-existent. This highlights the bearing capacity of well placed good quality hardcore material.

SIAMSA TIRE

Some extracts from the Siamsa Tire site investigation are highlighted. The site investigation which was comprehensive, indicated soft material to depths of 5 to 6m overlying rock and broken rock. As already explained, a piling solution was examined and discarded on cost grounds. (Ref. Fig. 14) It was also recognised that cost controlling of the piling itself would be very difficult for the reasons already outlined. The final solution used is highlighted in figure 15. The very soft material, overlying the site was excavated to depths varying from 2m to 5m. Heavy limestone rock, 300mm down, was then rolled in to a level within 2m of finished floor level. It was assumed that loss of this material into the soft silt and clays under would occur. This was confirmed during the contract when a loss of up to 300mm was seen to occur. At the 99m level, as indicated on figure 15, a heavy filter membrane was placed on top of the limestone and a further layer of 100mm down limestone was placed in 225mm layers to a depth of 1m. This was then very heavily rolled.

The filling contract was carried out some three months before work commenced on site on the superstructure. The reasons for the two stage contract were primarily political in order to get the project underway. However, there was a substantial technical benefit since the settlement in the fill could occur in the intervening three months. Also, the precontract filling was carried out at the end of a very dry summer, in very favourable ground conditions. The superstructure did not commence until the following March in what would have been difficult weather conditions. Settlement of the fill was monitored for a number of months up to and during the superstructure construction. No settlement was detected.

PROPOSED COUNTY COUNCIL OFFICES, ASHE MEMORIAL HALL, TRALEE

The initial site investigation on this project comprised a series of shell and augur and wagon drill holes. These indicated that rock occurred at high level at the western extremity of the site and at depths of the order of 6 to 7m over the remainder of the site. A foundation option using piles seemed to be a good solution especially since the overburden was soft silty clay and the water table in the area was high. However, as part of the design process, it was decided to drive some test piles to monitor the vibrations on the adjacent Ashe Memorial Hall building. It was expected that these driven piles would reach a set at depths of the order of 7m.

Three piles were driven on site. All three failed to reach a set, even at depths of 25m. Ultimately, the operation was aborted because the contractor ran out of pile lengths.

The site was subject to numerous site investigations in order to try and determine the reason for the anomalies. Figure 21 highlights what was thought to be the existing nature of the limestone bedrock. To the west of the site, there appears to be no problem with massive bedrock occurring. However, to the east, the rock was very cavernous and broken with numerous swallow holes occurring.

The foundation solution ultimately proposed is highlighted in figures 21 and 22. Again, a raft was proposed, articulated at third points. An additional feature was the provision of a structural screed at a lower depth in order to reinforce the underside of the hardcore layer. At the time, this was considered to give additional tensile strength to the hardcore layer. An alternative option worth examining would have been the Siamsa solution of allowing heavy hardcore material to penetrate into the soft overburden.

Ultimately, for other reasons, this office development was not proceeded with and Kerry Co. Council carried out a major redevelopment to then existing St. Catherine's Hospital, Rathass, Tralee.

KERRY CO. COUNCIL OFFICES, RATHASS, TRALEE.

In the text, site investigation data pertaining to the St. Catherine's Hospital site is illustrated. The development consisted of an extension to the existing building on the front elevation plus a new office block to the rear. The site investigation data again highlights the anomalous nature of the underlying limestone. Another feature noted during site investigations was the fact that air caverns occurred in the overburden itself. This was obviously very worrying in the context of providing or assuming a loading capability for the overburden.

In this building, a raft type solution, (reference figure 26) was used. Very soft material was encountered on the new extension. This was dug out and replaced to a depth of the order of 1.4m with compacted limestone material.

A feature of this development was the attempt that was made to grout the cavities in the overburden. This involved drilling, over the extent of the raft, on a 2m x 2m grid. Any cavities encountered during this drilling process were then grouted using a 60% sand and 40% cement mix. Ultimately, some 60 cubic metres of cavities were grouted, at a cost of approximately of £15,000. (Ref. Fig. 27)

It is obviously difficult to accurately estimate the benefit of this grouting solution, given that loss of grout could occur into swallow holes either horizontally or vertically. Notwithstanding, this, some comfort can obviously be derived from the fact that 50 cubic metres of material was used. Also, the grouting process was carried out in such a way as to try and minimise grout loss. This involved drilling on a sequential basis and placing the initial grout at low pressures. These areas would then be regouted in the following days when it was hoped that any escape routes for the grout would have been blocked.

FIG. 1.

Report No. 989	TRIAL PIT RECORD	
Contract KILLERISK, TRALEE	Sheet No.	Trial Pit No. A
	Excavation Method Mechanical Excavator	
Location	Ground Level	
Client MALACHY WALSH	Date 29.4.87	

Description	Depth	Legend	Samples		
			Ref. No.	Type	Depth
MADE GROUND (gravel and cobbles in a clayey matrix)					
Soft grey clayey SILT with roots	1.10				
Peaty TOPSOIL	1.70				
Soft grey SILT with organic matter	1.90				
Peaty TOPSOIL	2.20				
Soft to firm yellow and brown mottled silty CLAY with gravel and roots	2.30				
Stiff grey claybound GRAVEL	3.00				
	3.20				

Ground Water Conditions Pit remained dry.

Remarks Generally stable.

FIG. 2.

Contract KILLERISK, TRALEE	Borehole No. 1 Sheet
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Location	Type and Diameter Cable Tool 200mm
Client MALACHY WALSH & PTNRS.	Ground Level
	Date 19.3.87

Description	Reduced Level	Legend	Depth	Samples			Field Records And Tests
				Ref. No.	Type	Depth	
GRAVEL and COBBLES in a brown sandy silt		x o	1.00	10401	D	1.0	(0.5)N31
Yellow and brown mottled clayey SILT		x x o	1.50	10402	D	1.5	(1.5)N9
Black peaty clayey SILT		x x x o	2.00	10403	D	2.0	
Yellowish brown clayey SILT with roots		x x x o	2.50	10404	D	2.5	(2.5)N13
Grey gravelly clayey SILT		x x x o	3.00	10405	D	3.0	
Soft black clayey SILT		x x x o	4.00	10406	D	4.0	(3.5)N3
Very soft grey gravelly clayey SILT		x x x o	6.00	10407	D	6.0	(4.5)N1
Very soft black sandy SILT		x x x o	10.50	10408	D	9.5	(6.5)N<1 (10.0)N1

Water Level Observations during Boring				
Date	Hole Depth	Casing Depth	Depth to Water	Remarks
19.3.87			4.5	First Strike
"	10.5	10.5	4.0	
"	10.5	0.0	4.0	

Remarks **Chiselling :**
0.1 - 0.3 1 hr.

Sample/Test key	C-Cone Penetration Test
U-Tube Sample	N-Blows/0.3 metres
D-Disturbed Sample	R-Refusal
W-Water Sample	V-Vane
S-Standard Penetration Test	

Contract <p style="text-align: center;">KILLERISK, TRALEE</p>	Borehole No. 2 Sheet
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Location	Type and Diameter <p style="text-align: center;">Cable Tool 200mm</p>
Client <p style="text-align: center;">MALACHY WALSH & PTNRS.</p>	Ground Level
	Date <p style="text-align: center;">26.3.87</p>

Description	Reduced Level	Legend	Depth	Samples			Field Records And Tests
				Ref. No.	Type	Depth	
Dark brown gravelly CLAY with cobbles		o	1.00	10421	D	1.0	(0.5)N31
Mottled brown/grey clayey SILT with gravel and roots		x	2.00				(1.5)N31
Soft to firm mottled yellow/grey/brown gravelly SILT GRAVEL contained in dark grey clayey silt		x	2.50	10422	D	2.5	(2.5)N13
		x	3.00	10423	D	3.0	(3.5)N19
Dark grey gravelly clayey SILT		o	4.00	10424	D	4.0	(4.5)N22
		x	6.00	10425	D	6.0	
Stiff black SILT at 6.0m.		x					

Water Level Observations during Boring					Remarks
Date	Hole Depth	Casing Depth	Depth to Water	Remarks	
26.3.87			0.5	First Strike	Chiselling : 0.5 - 1.5 ... 1 3/4 hrs. 3.5 - 4.0 ... 1 1/4 hrs.
"	6.0	6.0	4.1		
"	6.0	0.0	0.3		
					Sample/Test key U-Tube Sample O-Disturbed Sample W-Water Sample S-Standard Penetration Test C-Cone Penetration Test N-Blows/0.3 metres R-Refusal V-Vane

Contract KILLERISK, TRALEE	Borehole No. 3 Sheet
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Location	Type and Diameter Cable Tool 200mm
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Client MALACHY WALSH & PTNRS.	Ground Level Date 20.3.87 - 23.3.87
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Description	Reduced Level	Legend	Depth	Samples			Field Records And Tests
				Ref. No.	Type	Depth	
Stiff reddish brown clayey SILT with roots and some gravel Stiff mottled brown/grey gravelly clayey SILT Firm to stiff mottled yellow/grey sandy clayey SILT GRAVEL, contained in dark grey organic silt with roots Grey gritty silty GRAVEL Grey gritty GRAVEL with cobbles		x	1.00	10408	D	1.00	(0.5)N35
		x	1.50	10409	D	1.50	(1.3)N42
		x	2.50	10410	D	2.50	
		x	3.10	10411	D	3.00	(3.0)N26
		x	4.50	10412	D	4.00	(3.5)N23
		x	5.50	10413	D	5.00	(4.5)N35

Water Level Observations during Boring					Remarks
Date	Hole Depth	Casing Depth	Depth to Water	Remarks	
20.3.87			3.0	First Strike	Chiselling : 0.0 - 0.4 ... 2 hrs. 5.5 ... 1½ hrs.
23.3.87	5.5	5.5	3.1		
"	5.5	0.0	0.9		
					Sample/Test key C-Cone Penetration Test U-Tube Sample N-Blows/0.3 metres D-Disturbed Sample R-Refusal W-Water Sample V-Vane S-Standard Penetration Test

FIG. 6.

FIG. 7.

30N CONCRETE IN RAFT AND GROUND FLOOR SLAB.

New 125mm powerfloated concrete slab reinforced with A142 mesh.

50mm rigid insulation.

D.P.C.

275mm well compacted hardcore.

A192 mesh mesh top and bottom.

EXISTING HARDCORE SURFACE TO BE ROLLED WITH 15 PASSES OF ROLLER VIBRATING TO 18 TONS.

3T16 (REPEAT 3T16 UNDER EACH INTERNAL WALL).

50mm COVER TO ALL REINFORCEMENT IN RAFT.

ALL 16mm BARS TO BE LAPPED 700mm. MESH TO BE LAPPED 300mm IN EACH DIRECTION.

Malachy Walsh and Partners
 Consulting Engineers
 Boreenmanna Rd. Cork.
 Park House, 21 Denny Street Tralee •
 54 Old Street, London EC1V9AL

Title: **TYPICAL RAFT FOUNDATION DETAIL.**

Drq. No.	1142-753-01			
rev.	01			

FIG. 8.

FIG. 10.

Malachy Walsh and Partners Consulting Engineers 12 DENNY ST. TRALEE tel 066 24166 telex 28407			Project : PROPOSED NEW SIAMSIA SITE AT TRALEE CO KERRY	Drg No 1733/S1
Drawn MB	Date FEB 89	Scale 1:1000	SITE INVESTIGATION.	Rev.

Report No.		TRIAL PIT RECORD		IGSL	
Contract SIAMSA , TRALEE			Sheet No.	Trial Pit No. 1	
Location TRALEE, CO.KERRY			Excavation Method POCLAIN EXCAVATOR		
Client MALACHY WALSH AND PARTNERS			Ground Level		
			Date MARCH 1989		
Description	Depth	Legend	Samples		
			Ref. No.	Type	Depth
MADE GROUND CLAY RUBBLE ETC.(LOOSE)	0.75				
SOFT GREY BROWN MOTTLED ORGANIC VERY CLAYEY SILT					
FRAGMENTS OF GREY LIMESTONE WITH GREY BROWN SILTY CLAY	2.20				
REFUSAL OF EXCAVATOR AT 2.40	2.40				
Ground Water Conditions					
SURFACE WATER INGRESS COPIOUS WATER STRIKE AT 2.20.					
Remarks					
UNSTABLE IN FILL AND SOME COLLAPSE IN SILTS					

FIG. 11.

Report No.	TRIAL PIT RECORD			IGSL	
Contract SIAMSA, TRALEE		Sheet No.	Trial Pit No. 8		
Location TRALEE, CO. KERRY		Excavation Method POCLAIN			
Client MALACHY WALSH AND PARTNERS		Ground Level			
		Date MARCH 1989			
Description	Depth	Legend	Samples		
			Ref. No.	Type	Depth
MADE GROUND OF LOOSE RUBBLE WITH BRICK CONCRETE CLAY ETC.					
	1.90				
SOFT GREY BROWN MOTTLED VERY CLAYEY SILT WITH ORGANIC FIBRES.					
REFUSAL AT 4.60 POSSIBLY ON BEDROCK.	4.60				
Ground Water Conditions					
COPIOUS WATER IN FILL, UNABLE TO ASCERTAIN IF FURTHER WATER STRIKE AT 4.60					
Remarks					
UNSTABLE IN FILL, SOFT AND UNSTABLE IN SILTS					
FIG. 12					

SIAMSA TIRE - TRALEE

ROTARY PERCUSSIVE SCHEDULE

HOLE NO.	DEPTH	DESCRIPTION OF MATERIAL
1	0.00 - 0.50	Boulders, gravels
	0.50 - 7.00	Very soft SILT/CLAY
	7.00 - 10.00	Loose BOULDERS or BROKEN ROCK
	10.00 - 13.00	Good ROCK
2	0.00 - 9.00	Firm SILT or CLAY
	9.00 - 12.00	BOULDERS/BROKEN ROCK
	12.00 - 15.00	Medium to hard (Boulders/clay)
	15.00 - 16.00	Very hard (ROCK)
3	0.00 - 2.00	BOULDERS
	2.00 - 6.00	Soft to firm CLAYS
	6.00 - 9.00	Could be hard BOULDER CLAYS/BROKEN ROCK
	9.00 - 11.00	ROCK
4	0.00 - 0.40	GRAVEL and BOULDES
	0.40 - 2.60	CONCRETE
	2.60 - 7.00	BOULDERS and CLAY. Possibly BROKEN ROCK
	7.00 - 9.00	ROCK
5	0.00 - 3.00	Loose BOULDERS, GRAVELS very little SILT
	3.00 - 5.00	ROCK (Hard)
	5.00 - 7.00	Fractured ROCK

FIG. 13.

SIAMSA TIRE
GROUND BEAM LAYOUT

FIG. 14.

∇ 100
 EXISTING G.L.

100mm down crushed limestone,
 rolled in 225mm layers. Allow
 6 passes with roller vibrating
 to 10 tons.

∇ 99
 MEMBRANE LEVEL

Robusta filter membrane, 350g/m.

300-225mm crushed limestone rockfill
 backfilled in position in max. 400mm
 layers. Each layer either rolled
 with a roller vibrating to 10 tons
 or else rammed into position to the
 same level of compaction. Assume
 6 passes for roller.

∇
 EXTENT OF EXCAVATION

FIG. 15.

FIG. 16.

FIG. 17.

SITE INVESTIGATIONS LTD.

SOIL INVESTIGATION BORING RECORD

CONTRACT Offices Tralee

BOREHOLE No. WD 1

Report No. -

Order No.

Bored for Malachy Walsh & Partners,

Site Address Co. Kerry

Boring Commenced 5.6.81

Boring Completed 5.6.81

Type of Boring Wagon Drill

Diameter of Borehole 50 mm

Ground level - O.D.

Water Struck (1) 1.50m BGL (2) (3)

Standing Water Level -

Remarks All levels are related to ground level

Description of Strata	Depth		Thickness	Sample		
	From	To		No.	Type	Depth
Clay	0.00		3.65			
		3.65				
Rock or boulder	3.65		0.30			
		3.95				
Clay	3.95		1.55			
		5.50				
Rock or boulder	5.50		0.30			
		5.80				
Broken rock and clay	5.80		2.75			
		6.55				
Broken rock	8.55		4.25			
		12.80				

FIG. 18.

SITE INVESTIGATIONS LTD.

SOIL INVESTIGATION BORING RECORD

CONTRACT Offices Tralee

BOREHOLE No. WD 7

Report No. -

Order No.

Bored by Malachy Walsh & Partners

Site Address Co. Kerry

Boring Commenced 3.6.81

Boring Completed 3.6.81

Type of Boring Wagon Drill

Diameter of Borehole 50 mm.

Ground level - O.D.

Water Struck (1) - (2) (3)

Standing Water Level -

Remarks All levels are related to ground level

ASHE HALL.

Description of Strata	Depth		Thickness	Samples		
	From	To		Ref. No.	Type	Depth
Clay	0.00	4.25	4.25			
Broken rock and clay	4.25	7.30	3.05			
Rock	7.30	11.60	4.30			

FIG. 20.

FIG. 21.

Malachy Walsh and Partners

Consulting Engineers

Boreenmanna Rd. Cork tel. 962866

Drawn

Date 24-6-82

Scale 1:200.

PROPOSED NEW OFFICES
AT DENNY ST., TRALEE,
FOR KERRY CO. COUNCIL.

LONGITUDINAL SECTION.

Orig. No.

929/SK

Rev.

33

PROPOSED NEW OFFICES.

TYPICAL CROSS SECTION. 1:100.

FLOOR CONSTRUCTION - TYPICAL DETAIL. 1:50

CONSTRUCTION JOINT - TYPICAL DETAIL. 1:20

FIG. 22.

Malachy Walsh and Partners
Consulting Engineers
Boreenmanna Rd. Cork tel. 962866

PROPOSED NEW OFFICES
AT DENNY ST., TRALEE,
FOR KERRY CO. COUNCIL.

Drg No
929/SK5

Drawn *TR* Date 17-6-82 Scale As stated

GROUND FLOOR LEVEL
TRANVERSE SECTION & DETAILS.

Rev.

GAS TANK

LAUNDRY

BOILER HOUSE

OLD PHARMACY

OFFICE

SHELL & AUGER HOLES SHOWN THUS:

WAGON DRILL HOLES SHOWN THUS:

COBRA DRILL HOLES SHOWN THUS:

J.C.B. TRIALPITS SHOWN THUS:

☒ OIL TANKS

SHED

WORKSHOP

MORTUARY

SHED

WATER TANK

X1

X2

X3

4X

7

3

8

4

9

1

2

3

4

5

6

1

2

#1

#2

CLINIC

○
●
X
#

FIG. 23

CHURCH

Contract TRALEE - ST. CATHERINE'S	Type of Rig. Wagon Drill	Borehole No. 1 Sheet
Location CO. KERRY	Circulation Fluid Air	
Client MALACHY WALSH & PTNRS.	Bit size/Core Diameter 50mm	
	Casing Diameter	
	Ground Level	
	Date 2.7.86	

Description	Reduced Level	Legend	Depth	Core Run	Core Recovery %	ROD%	Field Records
TARMAC			0.15				
Brown gravelly CLAY							
ROCK			3.20				
VOID			3.80				
ROCK			4.30				
VOID			4.60				
ROCK			4.90				
Gravelly CLAY at 5.6 metres			5.60				

FIG. 24.

Report No. 868	DRILLING RECORD/ CORE LOG		IGSL
Contract TRALEE - ST. CATHERINE'S		Type of Rig. Wagon Drill	Borehole No. 4 Sheet
Location CO. KERRY		Circulation Fluid Air	
Client MALACHY WALSH & PTNRS.		Bit size/Core Diameter 50mm	
		Casing Diameter	
		Ground Level	
		Date 3.7.86	

Description	Reduced Level	Legend	Depth	Core Run	Core Recovery %	ROD%	Field Records
TARMAC			0.15				
Brown gravelly CLAY							
ROCK			2.00				
Soft drilling			2.40				
VOID			3.40				
ROCK			4.60				
			8.00				

FIG. 25.

FIG. 26.

FIG 27

**REMEDIAL MEASURES APPLIED TO THE
ENGINEERING SOLUTION OF KARST PROBLEMS**

*Dr Michael Creed
Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering
University College Cork*

⇒ What do geologist look
for that cannot be
seen from the
relatively with
rock 15%
= O/Sie drillings

Remedial measures applied to the engineering solution of Karst problems

Michael J. Creed

Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering,
University College,
Cork

INTRODUCTION

On the basis of usually incomplete historical records of sinkhole events in Ireland and a broad understanding of the underlying geology, large regions of the land surface, locally or nationally, may be regarded as prone to the development of sinkholes, which can give rise to sudden and severe settlement of the ground surface and shallow foundations. Working in such an environment is a matter of serious concern to engineers. Such concern is magnified by an incomplete understanding of the mechanisms of sinkhole formation, the difficulty of realistically assessing the risk of sinkhole occurrences in the future and indeed the emotional stress of trying to reconcile the low risk of a sinkhole event with possibly very serious consequences.

This paper is a brief overview of the engineering of foundations in karst terrain. In this context, the term 'remedial' is considered to apply equally to work carried out in the early stages of construction to minimize the risk of damage and to work carried out following the development of problems at some time during or after the end of construction. The perceived risk and consequences, together with economic implications, will influence the strategy adopted in any particular case.

Even in suspect karst limestone areas, sinkholes tend to occur infrequently and affect only a very small area of the land surface. As such it is easy to regard them as accidents of nature, which impinge on the unfortunate victim, be it property owner or engineer. While sinkholes do occasionally occur naturally, there is considerable evidence from international research that the great majority of sinkholes are man induced, i.e., they are triggered directly by man made changes to the landscape and/or changes to the surface water and ground water regime (Newton, 1986; Daoxian, 1987; Buttrick & Roux, 1993). The fact that sinkholes may be directly induced by engineering works necessitates that the potential problems be considered as an integral part of the planning and design process for projects in karst areas.

SINKHOLE FORMATION IN AN ENGINEERING TIME SCALE

In order to appreciate the engineering implications of a karst environment, it is important to distinguish between the geological and engineering time scales. The root cause of surface settlement and collapse problems in soils overlying karst limestone lies in the development of cavity systems in the bedrock over a long period of time in the geological past. In the context of an engineering time scale, however, further erosion of the bedrock may be regarded as insignificant and the underlying karst topography may be considered to be fully developed, except perhaps where wastewater of a low pH is discharging into the ground. The existence of openings in the top of the bedrock gives rise to the possibility of the downward migration of the overlying soil into the rock cavities. When such downward migration of soil propagates eventually to the ground surface, causing a sudden settlement of the ground surface, a sinkhole develops. Thus, the engineering problems lie in the development of voids within the soil, rather than the rock.. According to Williams & Vineyard (1976) in a study involving 97 surface collapses in Missouri, U.S.A., "Although cavern roof collapse in bedrock has been cited as a cause of catastrophic sinkhole formation, no contemporary event that could be attributed directly to this cause has been observed".

Broad regional studies of sinkhole events, based on analysis of numerous case histories, provide important information for engineers:

- (1) While the fundamental reason for sinkholes lies in the existence of cavities in bedrock at depth, sinkhole development due to the collapse of bedrock is regarded as being such a rare event as to be of no significance in an engineering time scale (Newton, 1986).
- (2) Sinkholes arise from the collapse of the overlying soil into pre-existing cavities in the bedrock.
- (3) There is considerable evidence from numerous case histories that the vast majority of sinkholes are induced by the activities of man. The two main triggering events are believed to be the lowering of the ground water table to below rockhead level and inundation of potential sinkholes by surface water due to alteration of surface water drainage patterns as a result of engineering works.

Daoxian (1987) has described the occurrence of 758 large sinkholes between 1968 and 1982 around Shuicheng city in China, as 14 wells were successively put into use for water supply purposes, causing a water table drawdown of 10m-20m from an original level at a shallow depth below the ground surface. Moore (1988) estimated, in a study of highway related sinkholes in East Tennessee, U.S.A., that 85% of the 72 sinkholes studied were 'induced', with the vast majority of them occurring along unsealed roadside trench drains, the cause being inundation of potential collapse zones by surface water.

It is important for the engineer to recognize that the existence of underlying karst limestone is merely an indicator of potential sinkhole problems. Whether or not such unwelcome potential will be realised depends very much on the nature of the overlying soil and on hydrogeological changes, many of which may be man induced.

ENGINEERING STRATEGY FOR KARST AREAS

The underlying bedrock geology would suggest that a significant proportion of the land surface in Ireland could be regarded as having a potential for the development of sinkholes (Drew, 1995). However, on the basis of known incidences, the risk of sinkholes occurring on any particular site must be regarded in general as very small. Where significant development has taken place in the Cork area, there is limited evidence that some areas may be more susceptible to sinkholes than others. However, it is difficult to make a preliminary assessment of the risk potential of a particular site in the absence of a well documented history of previous sinkhole incidents. A comprehensive database along the lines proposed by Beese (1995) would be a very useful resource for the planning of future projects.

The normal practice of increasing the number of boreholes to provide additional information on suspect ground conditions does not provide a particularly efficient approach to locating sinkholes. In a broad review of the evaluation of subsidence potential due to subsurface cavities, Benson & Fountain (1984) have pointed out that, if one put down 500 cavity free boreholes on a 1 acre site in a suspect area, one could only be 50% sure, on the basis of a probabilistic assessment, that a subterranean cavity of 2.3m diameter was not present. While some geophysical techniques offer promise as a means of detecting cavities, they too cannot be guaranteed to produce definitive detection of concealed cavities. In the face of such uncertainty, a limited number of high quality boreholes, interpreted by a geologist experienced in local conditions, would appear to offer the best means of establishing the risk potential of a site. A large number of percussion drilled holes to establish depth to bedrock and to prove rock is not a substitute for coring of the rock, but may be very useful once tentative decisions have been made about foundations. Raghu et al. (1984) have described a methodology for establishing a site specific correlation between the penetration resistance during air track (wagon) drilling and the soil and rock conditions. The application of the Foundation Quality Index (FQI) derived from the penetration rates to foundation design is summarized in Appendix 1, which is an extract from Raghu et al. (1984). All boreholes should be backfilled with grout in a suspect karst area, so as to ensure that they do not act as conduits for concentrated water flows at some future time.

Where it has been estimated that there is some risk of sinkhole formation on the site, precautions should be taken with respect to control of surface and waste water in order to minimize the risk of inundation of potential sinkholes. Roux (1987) has recommended as follows for developments on low risk dolomitic karst sites in Transvaal Province, South Africa: French drains are unacceptable; no damming (or ponding) of water is allowed; all water bearing services and ditches must be watertight, with sewerage lines fitted with couplings allowing limited movement without leakage; all streets and parking areas must be sealed with bitumen or concrete with sealed joints; excavations and trenches for foundations, cables, pipes, etc., must be backfilled with moist soil compacted in layers of 150mm to attain the same order of permeability as the original undisturbed material. Such good practice forms a basic preventative strategy, which should be generally adopted without incurring significant additional costs.

If, on the basis of the site investigation, it is possible to divide the site into zones of differing risk, the fundamental strategy should be to locate structures, particularly sensitive structures, in the zones of lowest risk. Such decisions should not in general imply any significant additional costs.

Should the risk of settlement due to sinkholes be perceived to be substantive, one may consider a range of preventative strategies, ranging from remediation of the voided soil and rock to avoidance of potential problems by founding directly in sound rock. Alternatively, one could adopt a wait and see attitude and put in place a remedial strategy, which could be applied should any problems arise at a future date. It is a case of weighing the initial indefinite costs of preventative measures against the risk of serious problems and associated unknown costs at some future date. It is important to strike a balance between the possible waste of resources on unnecessary preventative work and the possible consequences of not doing so. In such an uncertain scenario it is imperative that the client be fully briefed on the issues involved and be willing to take responsibility for the risks associated with savings in initial costs.

The remainder of this paper is devoted to consideration of the various preventative and remedial strategies, applicable to structures and highways. While there is considerable overlap in the relevant technology, preventative and remedial works are considered separately.

PREVENTATIVE STRATEGIES FOR STRUCTURES

In addition to the basic zoning and water management measures, a number of specific preventative strategies may be adopted, depending on the ground conditions and structures. These may range from modified shallow foundations through ground improvement measures to deep foundations bearing on sound rock.

Shallow foundations

Where the perceived risk of sinkholes is low and the near surface soils provide a nominally sound bearing stratum, the most cost effective approach may be to use conventional shallow foundations and adopt a wait and see attitude to possible future sinkholes. For masonry walls on strip foundations, the potentially most damaging settlement is one that would lead to a hogging mode of deformation, where cracks would develop from the top of the structure down. Continuous strip reinforcement at one or more levels within the masonry and/or a continuously reinforced concrete ring beam at wall plate level are minor modifications, which may be incorporated in standard house construction, to mitigate the effect of hogging movement in the event of ground subsidence. Top reinforcement to a standard house foundation may be provided quite simply by constructing the uppermost layer of the solid rising wall as a cavity wall and placing continuous reinforcement into the concrete or mortar filled cavity to provide a doubly reinforced strip foundation (Figure 1). Extending the strip foundations a short distance beyond the corners of the building would also tend to mitigate the effects of a localized collapse under the corner of the structure.

Where the rock is encountered at shallow depth, conventional strip or pad footings may be used. As the rock surface may be very irregular with deep soil slots between rock pinnacles, it may not be possible to determine the actual rock profile until the foundation has been prepared. In such circumstances, it is important to have in place strategies for preparing the rock surface for foundations. Small soil pockets may be cleaned out and filled with lean concrete (Figure 2), while it will be necessary to bridge deeper soil slots using reinforced concrete ground beams (Figure 3).

Having estimated the likely maximum size of cavity, a raft foundation may be designed so as to be capable of bridging a single such cavity, occurring anywhere under the raft (Figure 4). This approach was adopted in a recent major project in the Cork area (Langford & Kavanagh, 1993).

Ground improvement

Karst sites are often characterized by variable ground conditions, with soft zones being associated with past sinkhole activity. A number of ground improvement techniques have been applied for the dual purpose of improving the geotechnical characteristics of the near surface soils and filling cavities in the soil and bedrock. Henry (1989) has described the use of dynamic compaction, stone columns, slurry grouting and compaction grouting for pre-construction soil improvement on a number of sites, so as to facilitate the use of shallow foundations (Figure 5). Dynamic compaction and stone columns would be appropriate only to greenfield sites, as they would be likely to trigger sinkhole collapses during the ground treatment, threatening existing structures.

The injection of high slump sand/cement slurry grout into the soil and rock through a grid of holes offers the possibility of virtually completely filling all the voids penetrated in the soil and rock, to provide a platform for conventional shallow foundations. Where an extensive cavity system is encountered in the bedrock, very high grout takes may arise as the grout spreads easily to fill cavities outside the zone specifically requiring treatment. Low slump (<50mm) compaction grouting provides an alternative approach with many advantages. The grout will fill only large voids, will tend to travel a shorter distance from the grout hole and may be used to compact loose soil when the grout is pressurized. Welsh (1988) has described in detail the application of compaction grouting to provide economical solutions to foundation problems in new construction work in karst topographies. In one case history, the construction of a 1200 MW coal-fired power station, compaction grouting gave rise to an estimated \$6m or 50% saving in foundation costs, by facilitating shallow foundations on the improved ground. The paper by Welsh (1988) contains details on both specification and performance monitoring for two case histories.

Piled foundations

Where it is decided to found the structures directly in sound rock at depth, either driven or cast in situ piles may be used. While piles driven to refusal in the limestone bedrock would in general provide the nominally cheapest solution, difficulties may arise due to poor tip contact on a steeply dipping rock surface and highly variable pile lengths, as is often the case in karst limestone. Knott et al. (1993), in a review of 30 bridge projects in karst in Pennsylvania, have described a project, where driven H piles

were used successfully under one abutment and abandoned under the other one in favour of minipiles socketed into the bedrock.

Drilled reinforced concrete piled foundations offer many advantages, which may outweigh their probably nominally greater cost. They offer the possibility of drilling into the rock at each pile location and are easily adaptable to varying length requirements. In the case of large diameter drilled piles imposing a considerable load in end bearing on the rock, it would be advisable to wagon drill the underlying rock to ensure that the pile is not bearing directly over a cavity in the rock. Such concerns do not arise in the case of small diameter drilled piles, where the pile is socketed sufficiently far into the rock to ensure that the load may be transferred to the rock through skin friction rather than end bearing. The technology for constructing such piles is well developed in Ireland.

PREVENTATIVE STRATEGIES FOR HIGHWAYS

The previously quoted study by Moore (1988) of highway related sinkholes provided strong evidence that the vast majority of such sinkholes occur along unsealed roadside trench drains, the cause being inundation of potential collapse zones by surface water. Similar observations have been made by others. Any works which remove the existing soil cover and direct concentrated water flows towards suspect areas would be expected to give rise to an increased risk of sinkhole formation. Thus, there is a greater potential for sinkhole problems in areas of cut, where there is a general reduction in the thickness of protective soil cover. One would expect that the risk of development of sinkholes due to surface water ingress within the actual highway corridor would be greatest during construction, when the formation is exposed to the elements. Once the highway surface is sealed, the surface water triggering mechanism would tend to be confined to the areas beyond the pavement.

The most effective basic preventative strategy is the provision of sealed drains, together with roadside kerbs, to dispose of surface runoff from the highway. Moore (1988) recommends that paved drainage ditches be used in general throughout suspect karst areas. The normal Irish practice of using unjointed concrete pipes in trenches backfilled with free draining material appears to be inappropriate in suspected karst areas. The use of a system of sealed drains discharging either into an existing stream or to a location some distance away from the highway pavement, with the trench being backfilled with the excavated material, offers a cost effective means of reducing the risk of sinkhole formation during the life of the highway.

Where there is a substantial soil cover over bedrock and a history of deep sinkholes, sinkhole development under the pavement, leading to possible sudden collapse of the road surface, may be of serious concern. The preventative measures discussed for structures could be equally applied to a road pavement, though at a high cost. A more cost effective preventative strategy would be the incorporation of geotextile reinforcement, for example, in the form of a geogrid, into the bottom of the structural road pavement in a cut area or within the general embankment fill in a fill area. Such reinforcement could be designed to enable a small cavity to be bridged with small surface settlements (serviceability limit state) and a larger one to be bridged with

substantial surface settlements (ultimate limit state) to provide adequate warning of collapse and allow remedial measures to be taken.

In describing the problems encountered during construction of a large commercial development in karst terrain, Vandeveld & Schmitt (1988) comment as follows: "Construction phase observation of rain flooded areas was found to be an unpredictable but advantageous method of locating solution features. The repeated and heavy loads imposed by scrapers was also found to be a valuable tool in locating incipient dropouts." This experience would suggest that in the Irish climate, there may be some advantage in exposing suspect formations to the elements for an extended period, so as to encourage potential sinkholes to occur before construction of the pavement. This could also be regarded as a preventative strategy.

PLUGGING THE SINKHOLE

Where a fully developed sinkhole appears either during construction or later, it is best to plug it directly so as to seal the conduit down into the caved rock. Where the bedrock is at shallow depth and the throat of the sinkhole at the top of the bedrock is clearly visible or may be exposed by excavation, normal good practice is to plug the throat with lean mix concrete, on top of which are placed layers of compacted fill up to formation or ground level (Figure 6). Alternatively, the throat may be plugged with clean rockfill, the top of which is sealed off by concrete or a low slump grout. If some natural drainage is to be allowed through the plugged throat, the concrete capping may be replaced by a graded filter or permeable fill overlying a geotextile separating membrane (Figures 7,8).

Moore (1988) advocates the use of 'chunk rock' backfill to bridge the cavity, with detailed recommendations as follows:

"The induced collapse is excavated down to in-place bedrock or pinnacles. Clean chunk rock is backfilled into the excavated collapse (a geofabric may be used along the bottom of the collapse with placement of the rock backfill on top of the fabric).

The chunk rock backfill should be clean non-degradable limestone or sandstone free from shale or clay; at least 50% (by volume) of the rock should be 0.3m to 1m in the longest dimension with no more than 15% by volume passing the 5 cm screen; the maximum size of chunk rock shall be 1m.

The chunk rock backfill is to be choked off at the top by using crusher run material, geofabrics or concrete.

The ditchline should be paved, preferably with concrete; polyethylene sheeting or other impervious geofabrics may be utilized beneath the paved ditch."

In cases where it is not possible to locate the throat of the sinkhole at the surface of the rock, the precise extent of the sinkhole remains unclear. The common practice of simply filling the hole with granular fill may fill the void but do little to solve the problem in the long term, unless the supply of surface water which may have triggered the collapse is positively diverted elsewhere. Having cleared all loose material from the hole, the bottom of the hole should be filled with rockfill, over which is placed well

graded crushed rock, to provide a structure capable of arching across a possible future throat. The hole should be filled to formation with compacted layers of a low permeability soil, so as to ensure an effective soil plug, which will prevent further ingress of surface water into this suspect zone.

REMEDIAL WORK FOR STRUCTURES

The technical literature contains many examples of sinkhole subsidence effects, many of them catastrophic, on structures. For example, Canace & Dalton (1984) describe the complete collapse of a three storey residence into a crater caused by sinkhole development associated with a broken water main.

Once a subsidence problem develops in the vicinity of a structure, it is necessary to carry out remedial work as quickly as possible without further threatening the stability of the structure. Grouting is commonly used to fill subterranean voids, improve the loosened soils, provide needle piles down to sound rock and to raise the foundations. While high slump slurry grout is often used, low slump compaction grout appears to offer a technically better and more economic solution. Henry (1987) describes the use of compaction grouting to remediate a dwelling house, subject to sinkhole subsidence, where slurry grouting had previously failed.

Goehring & Sayed (1989) describe a case history, where a 1.37m diameter prestressed concrete wastewater pipe was completely undermined over a distance of 15m by a sinkhole collapse. The large void was filled with sand, followed by a grouting programme, comprising cement grouting of the deep soils to remediate the sinkhole and chemical grouting of the sand for 6m directly beneath the pipe to ensure long-term support for the pipe.

Where a structure is clearly undermined by the presence of a sinkhole, positive action to strengthen the foundations is of necessity required. For a structure merely threatened by a nearby sinkhole, the course of action is less clear. Where a number of property owners are involved, the technical course of action may well be dictated by legal rather than structural considerations. In the case of a problem confined to a one owner site, a minimum approach would include some wagon drilled holes in the vicinity of important threatened foundations and the previously described precautionary measures with respect to surface and waste water. Provided the owner was prepared to accept responsibility for the risk of future sinkhole occurrences, a wait and see attitude could be adopted.

REMEDIAL WORK FOR HIGHWAYS

According to Moore (1988), most of the problems encountered during the life of a highway are likely to occur in unsealed surface water drains at the edge of the highway. Unless the sinkhole was sufficiently large to threaten the integrity of the pavement, it would be difficult to justify elaborate remedial measures on an isolated sinkhole. At a minimum, the damaged drainage pipes should be replaced and the loose disturbed material should be removed from the sinkhole and replaced by compacted fill. In the case of a large sinkhole or a number of smaller ones in unsealed drains,

consideration could be given to the replacement of the drains by a sealed system. Where this is impractical, minimum measures and a wait and see attitude is probably the best approach.

Where a sinkhole affects the structural road pavement, extensive remedial measures could involve grouting and/or geotextiles. A grid of carefully executed wagon drilled exploratory holes should give an indication of both loose material and voided areas beneath the pavement. Compaction grouting of voids and loose soil, under a pressure which would give rise to a small uplift of the pavement surface, is one possible solution. Alternatively, the area surrounding the subsidence could be excavated and the sinkhole plugged and filled, with a geotextile being incorporated at the base of the structural pavement or in the underlying compacted fill. Bonaparte & Berg (1987) describe such an approach to the remediation of a very large sinkhole, where 13 layers of geogrid were incorporated in the compacted fill to provide a 12m wide 'bridge' over a plugged sinkhole.

Belesky et al. (1987) describe an interesting case history of an airport runway pavement, experiencing 7-10 sinkholes per year. Following very detailed site investigation, it was concluded that up to half of the runway pavement area was seriously at risk from sinkholes. So great were the estimated full remedial costs that the airport authorities decided to adopt a wait and see attitude, involving a regular monitoring programme and repair of cavities, which resulted in pavement collapse. It was a decision to accept a limited though real risk in order to achieve significant cost savings.

SOME LOCAL CASE HISTORIES

Soon after a broken water main, located under the road in a suburban residential estate, was reported to the local authority, structural damage to two directly adjacent houses in a terrace of seven units was observed. Cracking was eventually reported in all seven houses. Cavities and cracking were encountered in the overburden in two of the trial pits. Limestone bedrock was typically 5m to 8m below ground level. The location of the caved trial pits and the pipe burst relative to the most severely damaged house suggested a fissure system with a north-south orientation. It was decided to pressure grout the overburden and bedrock under all seven houses. While the grout volumes were very large under the structurally damaged houses, they were, with minor exceptions, small elsewhere. This evidence would suggest that the saturation of the overburden by water emanating from the pipe burst triggered the subsidence of the overburden into an underlying cavity beneath the structurally damaged houses. The cost of the remedial works amounted to a sizeable proportion of the market value of the seven houses.

During a road construction project, four sinkholes, 1.0m to 2.4m in diameter, appeared in succession during the summer months, at a stage when a shallow cut had been excavated to formation level for some time. A geological assessment of the site suggested that the zone of highest risk of further subsidence comprised a 300m length, which included all four sinkholes. Additional boreholes put down in the vicinity of the sinkholes encountered infilled and open cavities in the underlying limestone, which was

a minimum of 7m below ground level. The water table was found to be close to rockhead. In the light of the sinkhole occurrences, measures were required to minimize the risk of a sudden collapse of the road pavement during use. Drilling and grouting of the soils and rock on a closely spaced grid was considered and rejected on the grounds of an unknown but high cost. On the basis that the risk of further subsidence sinkholes under the sealed pavement was likely to be lower than for the exposed formation, it was decided to provide minimum reinforcement of the flexible pavement to prevent the sudden appearance of surface voids on the high speed dual carriageway. A polyester geogrid, with a nominal breaking load of 100 kN/m, was placed near the bottom of the sub-base. It was estimated that this geogrid would support the pavement and traffic over a 1m diameter cavity in the long term. At a cavity diameter of 3m, it was estimated that a surface depression of the order of 200mm would develop under the weight of the pavement alone, giving clear warning of the development of an underlying subsidence sinkhole.

About 4 km to the west of this site, where some 1m to 2.5m of gravel overburden was overlying limestone bedrock, a 6m deep limestone quarry was excavated to the south of the road. During the course of the works, while the quarry was kept dry by pumping from sumps, a total of thirteen subsidence sinkholes, 0.4m to 1.6m in diameter, appeared in groups in the gravel along the line of the road, over a distance of some 200m. The formation of these sinkholes would appear to have been directly related to the drawdown of the water table in the underlying bedrock. Karst features were found to be extensively developed in the limestone bedrock in the quarry, with both open and infilled voids being present. Since the original water table has been restored, no further sinkholes have been observed on the exposed gravel formation over a period of many months, during which there has been heavy construction traffic on the site. If there are no further significant occurrences during construction, it may be inferred that the risk of further sinkholes under a sealed pavement is sufficiently low as to preclude the need for reinforcement of the pavement.

CONCLUSIONS

While strategies to prevent the occurrence of or limit the damage of sinkholes in engineering projects in karst areas are available, there is always a risk associated with such construction. Given the generally low risk of serious problems even in suspect karst areas, elaborate and costly preventative strategies are likely to be justified only in exceptional cases. The engineer is obliged to focus the site investigation so as to evaluate possible karst features, to recommend basic precautionary measures in suspect areas and to advise the client of the possible risks associated with different construction strategies in karst. It is essential for the client to accept responsibility for the risk of possible future problems, where capital cost savings are achieved by limiting the extent of investigation and preventative measures. In cases where future problems arise, the remedial action should attempt to 'cure' the problem at a particular location, by investigating it as fully as possible and sealing the voids.

REFERENCES

- Beese, A.P. (1995) A database for subsidence sinkholes in the Cork district. GSI/IEI Karst Seminar, Cork, 27 February 1995.
- Belesky, R.M., Hardy, H.R. & Strouse, F.F. (1987) Sinkholes in airport pavements: Engineering implications. In *Karst Hydrogeology: Engineering & Environmental Applications* (eds. Beck, B.F. & Wilson, W.L.), A.A. Balkema, 411-417.
- Benson, R.C. & Fountain, L.J.L. (1984) Evaluation of subsidence or collapse potential due to subsurface cavities. In *Sinkholes: Their Geology, Engineering & Environmental Impact* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 201-215.
- Bonaparte, R. & Berg, R.R. (1987) The use of geosynthetics to support roadways over sinkhole prone areas. In *Karst Hydrogeology: Engineering & Environmental Applications* (eds. Beck, B.F. & Wilson, W.L.), A.A. Balkema, 437-445.
- Buttrick, D.B. & Roux, P. (1993) The safety of high density informal settlements on the dolomites of South Africa. In *Applied Karst Geology* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 291-294.
- Canace, R. & Dalton, R. (1984) A geological survey's cooperative approach to analyzing and remedying a sinkhole related disaster in an urban environment. In *Sinkholes: Their Geology, Engineering & Environmental Impact* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 343-348.
- Daoxian, Y. (1987) Environmental and engineering problems of karst geology in China. In *Karst Hydrogeology: Engineering & Environmental Applications* (eds. Beck, B.F. & Wilson, W.L.), A.A. Balkema, 1-11.
- Drew, D. (1995) The nature of karstic environments and the associated environmental problems, GSI/IEI Karst Seminar, Cork, 27 February 1995.
- Goehring, R.L. & Sayed, S.M. (1989) Mann road sinkhole stabilization; A case history. In *Engineering and Environmental Impacts of Sinkholes and Karst* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 319-325.
- Henry, J.F. (1989) Ground modification techniques applied to sinkhole remediation. In *Engineering and Environmental Impacts of Sinkholes and Karst* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 327-332.
- Knott, D.L., Newman, F.B., Rojas-Gonzalez, L.F. & Gray, R.E. (1993) Foundation engineering practice for bridges in karst areas in Pennsylvania. In *Applied Karst Geology* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 225-230.
- Langford, P. & Kavanagh, J. (1993) SANDOZ Pharmaceutical Project at Ringaskiddy. Trans. I.E.I., 1993.
- Moore, H. (1988) Treatment of Karst Along Tennessee Highways. In *Geotechnical Aspects of Karst Terrains*, Geotechnical Special Publication No. 14, ASCE, 133-148
- Newton, J.G. (1986) Development of Sinkholes Resulting From Man's Activities in the Eastern United States. U.S. Geological Survey Circular 968, 54p.
- Raghu, D., Lifrieri, J.J. & Rhyner, F.C. (1984) Use of percussion probes for the design and construction of foundations in and on carbonate formations. In *Sinkholes: Their Geology, Engineering & Environmental Impact* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 171-176.
- Roux, P. (1987) The engineering-geological evaluation of sites proposed for development in the dolomite karst regions of southern Africa. In *Karst Hydrogeology: Engineering & Environmental Applications* (eds. Beck, B.F. & Wilson, W.L.), A.A. Balkema, 331-336.
- Sowers, G.F. (1984) Correction and protection in limestone terrane. In *Sinkholes: Their Geology, Engineering & Environmental Impact* (ed. Beck, B.F.), A.A. Balkema, 373-378.
- Vandevelde, G.T. & Schmitt, N.G. (1988) Geotechnical Exploration and Site Preparation Techniques for Large Mall in Karst Terrain. In *Geotechnical Aspects of Karst Terrains*, Geotechnical Special Publication No. 14, ASCE, 86-96.
- Welsh, J.P. (1988) Sinkhole Rectification by Compaction Grouting. In *Geotechnical Aspects of Karst Terrains*, Geotechnical Special Publication No. 14, ASCE, 115-132
- Williams, J.H. & Vineyard, J.D. (1976) Geological indicators of catastrophic collapse in karst terrane in Missouri. National Academy of Science, Transportation Research Record 612, 31-37.

Appendix 1 Extract from Raghu, D. et alia. (1984)

Determination of the Foundation Quality Index

The correlation between the penetration resistance and the bearing capacity of the rock, referred to as the "Foundation Quality Index" (FQI) was defined as follows:

$$\text{Foundation Quality Index (FQI)} = \frac{\text{Penetration resistance in seconds/foot}}{\text{Penetration resistance in seconds/foot for intact competent rock}} \times 100$$

The penetration resistance for intact competent rock is unique to each site, dependent upon the type of rock and the kind of equipment used. For this particular site the penetration resistance for intact competent rock was determined to be 40 seconds per foot within the finer grained, thinly bedded rock member. In order to account for difference in penetration rates observed between the differing rock units, the penetration rates obtained from the probes made within the massive coarse grained rock member were increased by multiplying each observed rate by 1.43. In this manner, these penetration rate values were normalized to those observed in the fine grained member upon which most of the foundations were established.

The allowable net bearing capacity of a rock exhibiting FQI values between 75 and 100 percent was observed to be 40 tons per square foot. This rock would be similar to the Class 2-65 rock as described by the New York City Building Code (1970). Similarly, rocks exhibiting lower FQI values could be assigned allowable bearing values dependent upon observable quality and could also be correlated with equivalent classes of rock as described in that code. Any rock zone exhibiting FQI values greater than 100 percent were arbitrarily set equal to 100 percent for calculation purposes. Table I has been prepared and shows the relationships between the FQI value, type of rock and allowable bearing capacity observed for the subject site. For purposes of comparison, the corresponding classes of rock as defined by the New York City Building Code and their nominal values for bearing are also presented in Table I.

FQI values less than 30 percent indicate soil conditions. Values less than 15 percent were indicative of soil filled cavities, very soft seams or voids in the bedrock. In this case no bearing value or type was assigned.

TABLE I

MATERIAL DESIGNATION TYPE	FQI %	ALLOWABLE BEARING VALUES (TSF)	EQUIVALENT N.Y.C. BUILDING CODE CLASS ALLOWABLE BEARING VALUES (TSF)*	
A	75-100	20-40	2-65	40
B	40-75	7-20	3-65	20
C	30-40	4-7	4-65	12
D	15-30	Appropriate Soil Values	N/A	N/A

* Values of class 2-65, 3-65 and 4-65 rock may be increased with embedment in accordance with N.Y.C. Building Code Requirements.

Figure 1. Doubly reinforced strip foundation

Figure 2 (after Sowers (1984))

Figure 3. (after Sowers (1984))

Figure 4 (after Sowers (1984))

Slurry Grouting

Compaction Grouting

Dynamic Deep Compaction (DDC)

Vibro-Compaction and
Vibro-Replacement

Figure 5. Ground Improvement Techniques (after Henry (1988))

Figure 6. (after Sowers (1984))

Figure 7 (after Sowers (1984))

Figure 8 (after Sowers (1984))

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SEMINAR

Investigation of Karst Areas and Remedial Action
Adopted for Roads and Structures
27th. February 1995

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